

ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION: A PROBLEM OR LIFESTYLE OF YOUNG LEADERS

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Annotation: This thesis discusses the problem of academic procrastination in young leaders and its occurrence in social life.

Key words: laziness, academic procrastination, learning activity, cognitive interest, motivation.

Education is an important stage in everyone's life, but academic procrastination has reached alarming proportions in the current general availability of educational resources. The purpose of the work is to study the causes of procrastination, to study the types of procrastinators, to find an answer to the question: is procrastination a problem of the organization of the educational process or the lifestyle of students, as well as to find ways out of the current situation. The results of an anonymous survey of future young leaders showed that more than half of the respondents suffer from procrastination. Identified causes of procrastination, including low or lack of motivation to study, inability to plan one's activities, insufficient basic knowledge and poorly formed learning abilities, the presence of certain phobias, N. Milgram's classification together with allowed to analyze the characteristics of four types of procrastinators: perfectionist, neurotic, rebellious and lucky. A detailed analysis of the types of procrastinators allows us to consider academic procrastination as a problem related to the socio-psychological factors of students, which in turn model their lifestyle. Only interested psychologists and caring teachers can solve the problem.

Procrastination exists as much as humanity itself. Even in early societies, people were lazy and put things off, even though a delay in planting could lead to starvation. At the same time, since ancient times, the attitude to an idle lifestyle was completely negative, because a lazy person in any society, regardless of culture and religion, was considered a free, excessive mouth.

From a medical point of view, laziness is a natural reaction of the human body, which is manifested in the brain's attempt to protect it from a stressful situation if the work is performed at the limit of strength. (14th century) lazy people are in the fifth circle of hell. As society entered the industrial age, it began

to postpone a number of jobs more often, as machines gradually replaced the manual labor of people at individual stages of production [1].

Today, in the era of rapid development of technology, procrastination, flourishing, has a new scale and covers various areas of human activity, where education, unfortunately, is not an exception. In the scientific context, the term "procrastination" was introduced in the last century by the American publicist P. Ringenbach, but this phenomenon is now due to the availability of knowledge (after all, educational resources are at arm's length or a few clicks away) and most students is becoming more relevant due to the contradiction that has arisen between The purpose of the study is to determine the causes of procrastination among young managers, to determine the influence of individual psychological characteristics of students of organizational factors on regular procrastination of tasks, as well as to find ways to solve the existing problem.

Materials and research methods.

In an empirical study aimed at determining the dependence of the phenomenon of procrastination on the individual psychological characteristics of young leaders, the following assessment methods were voluntarily conducted: Self-regulation of the manifestation of laziness, developed by D. A. Bogdanova and S. T. Form, Student Procrastination Scale (PSS), Academic Procrastination Rating Scale by C. Leigh, L. Solomon and E. Rothblum. In addition to these psychodiagnostic scales, methods such as observation and interview, followed by synthesis and analysis of respondents' answers and summarization of results were used.

The main hypothesis of the study: academic procrastination is associated with individual psychological characteristics of young leaders, that is, they have low cognitive motivation, poorly formed learning skills, have difficulties in planning and organizing cognitive and other activities, Students who lack self-discipline and self-management skills are prone to academic procrastination.

Laziness is the devaluation of the desire to achieve success: inactivity of an enthusiastic nature, lack of diligence, lack of confidence in the goal, lack of motivation and readiness to carry out a certain activity, accumulated fatigue, along with the enjoyment of passive entertainment .

Procrastination is the voluntary postponement of planned activities despite negative consequences and negative emotional experiences. Thus, in contrast to laziness, which brings pleasure, procrastination is an irrational and uncomfortable behavior for the individual, both materially and psychologically.

There is a chronic neurotic type of procrastination. From other types of procrastinators, they are distinguished by excessive anxiety, often leading to panic attacks:

- + *running on the sides of the eyes;*
- + *the habit of biting nails;*
- + *tapping on the table with a pencil;*
- + *obsessive leg shaking;*
- + *looking at the clock or displaying many other ways of expressing your nervous energy.*

Due to self-doubt, they are not only afraid of making mistakes, but also do not want to offend anyone, and therefore they choose their words carefully, are slow to make decisions, and always hesitate. Chronic neurotics are extremely cautious and hesitant people, and it is very difficult for them to get out of their comfort zones. They are usually introverts who live in their heads. Procrastinators of this type suffer from hypengiophobia (irrational fear of responsibility). Although they are intelligent, their emotional intelligence is very low, resulting in low self-esteem. Chronically annoying procrastinators depend on the opinions of others, and they constantly seek the approval, advice, and support of trusted friends, colleagues, and mentors.

Conclusions.

The study shows that academic procrastination is undoubtedly a problem caused by the socio-psychological factors of young leaders, which in turn model their lifestyle, and this problem can only be solved by experienced teachers and psychologists who are interested in it.

In conclusion, we emphasize that despite the many similar characteristics of the same type of procrastination, the choice of a certain method of combating the habit of procrastination is primarily determined by the individual psychological characteristics of the subject. The results of the study can be used in the process of coordinating the work of young teachers to eliminate the problem of delay in the activity environment and to prevent this problem.

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